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Population Dynamics Of Catfish (*Clarias lazera*) From River Gongola In Malleri Gombe State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Clarias lazera is one of the predominant fish species in the Malleri area of River Gongola. However, the fishery has been experiencing a gradual decline over time. There is a lack of recent data on the population dynamics and exploitation pattern of these species, which is essential for sustainable management. Accordingly, the aim of the study was to ascertain the population dynamics of Catfish (*Clarias lazera*) from river gongola in Malleri Gombe State Nigeria. Fish samples were obtained from local small-boat fishermen of malleri water body. A total of 659 samples were analyzed with the FiSAT II program (FAO-ICLARM Stock Assessment Tools) to estimate population parameters. The study observed fish lengths ranging from 8cm to 53cm. Fish weights varied between 1.71g to 838.4g. While fish morphometric such as length and weight were measured using standard measuring tape and electronic weighing balance (TH-1000). Length weight relationships were determined using the length and weight frequency data as an input. Length frequency data (LFD) as input on FiSAT 11 software were used to analyze growth parameters such as asymptotic length (L_{∞}), growth coefficient (K) and a growth performance index (ϕ'). Recruitment pulses were analyzed employing “recruitment” option. “Length Converted Catch Curve” option of the said FiSAT 11 was applied to determined mortality indices (which are M^{-yr} , F^{-yr} , and Z^{-yr}) of the fish species. The probabilities of capture at various lengths were $L_{25\%} = 11.24$ cm, $L_{50\%} = 13.79$ cm, and $L_{75\%} = 15.56$. Instantaneous mortality rates were calculated as $M = 0.37$ year⁻¹ for natural mortality, $F = 0.60$ year⁻¹ for fishing mortality, and $Z = 0.97$ year⁻¹ for total mortality. The highest score of 3.73 potential longevity (T_{max}) studied revealed that the species has 1.8 years, accordingly. Mortality parameters inferred total mortality (Z) of 3.38. Natural mortality fall within 2.21 to 2.29 and fishing mortality were in the range of 1.09 to 1.475. Exploitation ratio (E) revealed that 0.24% of the said fish species were optimally exploited ($E < 0.05$). The malleri water body is rich diverse living aquatic resources which is facing challenges of structural collapse unless management strategies are fully adopted. The host community should be made integral component of aquatic resources management team. And other means of livelihood should be made attractive to reduce pressure on aquatic resources.

Key words: *population dynamics, Catfish (Clarias lazera, Malleri water body Gombe State Nigeria.*

INTRODUCTION

Fish resources provide humans with affordable, high-quality animal protein. They also generate employment *opportunities* for a significant portion of the rural population and act as a source of raw materials for a wide range of industrial and recreational applications. (Wake and Geleto, 2019).

Freshwater ecosystems, which are essential to life as we know it on Earth, are the most vulnerable ecosystems worldwide (Gebremedhin; 2021) Fish resources have seen a range of changes in stock diversity and abundance despite their many benefits and vast species diversity due to structural changes in habitat, food composition, and unrestrained exploitation (Nazeef, and Yerima, 2023).

Malleri region of the River Gongola is a crucial breeding and feeding ground for a variety of fish species because of its distinct hydrological patterns and various fish species (Gordon *et al.*, 2018), However, anthropogenic stresses including overfishing, habitat degradation, and climate variability are posing an increasing danger to the sustainability of the fish populations in this area (Gordon *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, it is essential to comprehend the population dynamics of fish species in this area in order to create conservation and management plans that work (Gebremedhin, 2021)

Fisheries sustainability, biodiversity preservation, and the sustaining of ecosystems and human livelihoods are all dependent on fish population dynamics, which include growth, recruitment, mortality, and interactions with the environment (Gebremedhin, 2021)

Fish growth refers to the progressive increase in an individual fish's size, including its length, weight, and overall mass, over time. Unlike most animals, fish experience continuous growth throughout their lifespan, a trait known as indeterminate growth (Ahti *et al.*; 2020) the growth of fish is affected by a range of factors, including biological, genetic, and environmental influences (Abd El-Hack *et al.*; 2022)

Fish typically continue to grow throughout their lives, though their growth rate slows considerably once they reach adulthood and old age (Gatto, *et al.*; 2023) Fish can grow at different rates depending on their species, age, and environmental factors like oxygen levels, food availability, and water temperature (Zymarioieva *et al.*; 2024)

The rate at which fish in a population pass away from a variety of natural and man-made causes is known as "fish mortality." The size, composition, and long-term viability of fish populations are significantly influenced by mortality. The balance between fish births (recruitment) and deaths is affected, which influences total population growth or decline, making it a crucial component of population dynamics (Liu *et al.*, 2024)

Length-weight relationship (LWR) is of great importance in fishery assessments (Rodríguez-García *et al.*; 2023). Length and weight measurements in conjunction with age data can give information on the fish stock, age maturity, life span, mortality, growth and reproduction (Lai, *et al.*; 2023). Length-weight relationship of fish is widely recognized as an important tool in fisheries science especially in ecology population dynamic and stock management (Rodríguez-García *et al.*; 2023). For the reason that, the relationship permits estimating the weight of a specimen easily when the total length is known, these relationships are useful when rapid estimation of biomass is necessary (Zymarioieva *et al.*; 2024).

This study was carried out with the aim of assessing the length weight relationship, growth & recruitment pattern and mortality indices of Catfish (*Clarias lazera*) with the view of bridging the information gap on the condition of fish inhabiting the Malleri water body of river gongola.

Fish is said to exhibit isometric growth when length increases in equal proportion with body weight, the regression coefficient for isometric growth is '3' and values greater than '3' indicates allometric growth (Camp *et al.*; 2020) Fishing is one of the most important occupations of the people within the area of Malleri water body. Malleri water body is the dominant drainage system in Malleri town, the river being located in the tropical savanna.

Recruitment refers to the process by which young fish (juveniles) survive to join the adult population or fishable stock, usually after they have passed a stage of life where they are susceptible to fishing gears (Camp *et al.*; 2020)

Since recruitment directly affects the population's ability to replenish itself following losses from death (both natural and fishing-related) Generally speaking, recruitment is the point at which fish reach a size

that allows them to join the breeding or exploitable population (Hou *et al.*; 2020) Depending on the species, life stage, and management goals, this threshold varies, but it typically refers to fish reaching a size or age at which they become susceptible to fishing gear or are able to reproduce Geromont, and Butterworth, (2022) One of the most unpredictable parts of fish population dynamics is recruitment, which is extremely variable and impacted by a wide range of biological and environmental factors (Arevalo *et al.*; 2023) There can be significant variations in recruitment success from year to year due to environmental factors such as shifts in food supply, water temperature, or ocean currents (Ferreira *et al.*; 2024) Because it is the main means by which fish populations can recover from losses brought about by fishing and natural mortality, recruitment is a crucial component of fish population dynamics (Camp *et al.*; 2020)

On the other hand, a population may fall and possibly collapse due to overfishing if recruitment is unsuccessful or consistently low over a number of years (Arevalo *et al.*; 2023)

Mortality in exploited fisheries is either natural or fishing mortality (M and F, respectively) Natural Mortality (M) refers to death of fish as a result of natural causes, such as disease, old age, predation, temperature fluctuations, low oxygen levels, or competition for resources. Fish deaths caused by human activity, mainly fishing, are referred to as fishing mortality (F) (Björnsson *et al.*; 2020) this covers bycatch (species accidentally caught) as well as fishing for both commercial and recreational purposes. Both have a major role in declining fish populations especially when they exceed the population's natural ability to replenish through recruitment (Cali, (2024).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Malleri is a village situated in Kwami Local Government Area, which is one of the eleven local governments within Gombe State. It is located approximately 6 kilometers to the northeast of Gombe town. The village's geographical coordinates are latitude 10°29'35"N and longitude 11°12'36"E. The area lies within the northern Guinea savanna zone and covers a total land area of 1,787 km² (690 sq mi). According to the 2006 Census, the population of Kwami Local Government Area was 95,298. The altitude of Malleri is about 380 meters (1,247 feet) above sea level. The annual rainfall in the area averages around 800 cm, which is sufficient for a single farming season (Babangida, *et al.*; 2024).

The rainfall pattern is often irregular at the onset of the rainy season, which starts in April and can increase from 600 cm to 1,000 cm as the season progresses. Temperatures can reach a maximum of 34°C and drop as low as 16°C, with average temperatures typically high. Malleri is characterized by interior savannah woodland, which supports large-scale livestock farming as well as the cultivation of various agricultural products, both through rain-fed and irrigation methods. Common crops grown include onions, watermelon, spinach, rice, groundnuts, and maize (Babangida, *et al.*; 2024).

Figure I: Map of Malleri showing the study area (Remote sensing and GIS Laboratory Department of Geography, Gombe State University 2024)

Data collection

Data was collected by sampling fish monthly over a six-month period, covering both the dry and rainy seasons. Fish samples were obtained from local small-boat fishermen.

Fish Species Sampling

Samples of Catfish (*Clarias lazera*) were collected from randomly selected fishermen who used multifilament fishing gear in their activities from April to September 2024. Randomization was carried out by first identifying all fishermen operating in the study area who regularly used multifilament fishing gear. From this pool, a list of eligible fishermen was compiled. Using a simple random sampling method, fishermen were then selected by assigning each a number and using a random number generator (random number table) to ensure that each fisherman had an equal chance of being chosen. Fish samples Catfish (*Clarias lazera*) was then collected from the randomly selected individuals over the sampling period. This approach minimized selection bias and ensured a representative sample of the catch within the fishing community.

The study also identified the Fishery landing area as a primary hub where market vendors purchase fish directly from fishermen. Standard length (SL) and weight were measured to the nearest 0.1 cm and 0.1 g, respectively, using a measuring tape and a digital weighing scale (model TH - 1000), following the procedures outlined by Mendoza and Vigilia, (2024).

RESULTS

4.1 Length – Weight Relationship

The parameters for the length-weight relationship, including the constants "a" and "b" are presented in Table 1. The study recorded a sample of 659 individuals. Their SL ranged from 8cm to 53cm, and weights from 1.71g to 838.4g.

The allometric coefficient "b" for *C. lazera* was 3.0 was found to be isometric growth. These findings highlight species-specific growth patterns and provide a foundation for further ecological and fisheries-related assessments. This indicates that all sampled *Clarias lazera* samples demonstrated isometric growth, where both length and weight increases proportionally.

TABLE 1. Length- weight relationships of *Clarias lazera* collected from sampling site (malleri water body)

Fish species	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	Allometry
<i>C. Lazera</i>	0.184	3.0	Positive

Where: *a* = intercept of regression curve, *b* = slope of the regression curve

The growth parameters

The length frequency data was utilized to create a Powell-Wetterer plot (Dong *et al.*; 2019) which allowed for the determination of the initial asymptotic length (L_{∞}) the theoretical maximum length a fish would achieve if it continued to grow indefinitely and the ratio of Z/K . The calculated asymptotic length was then incorporated into the ELEFAN 1 software to derive the growth coefficient (K) based on the Von Bertalanffy Growth Formula (VBGF), ultimately providing the optimal growth curve for more accurate estimation of asymptotic length. Additionally, the length frequency distribution was analyzed using ELEFAN 1 (Vicentin *et al.*; 2018).

The growth parameters of the fish species were presented in Table These parameters include the asymptotic length (L_{∞} , growth constant per year (K^{-yr}), growth performance index (ϕ'), and the hypothetical maximum lifespan (T_{max}) for each species. The table shows that the L_{∞} value recorded for the species was 39.90cm, regarding the growth constant (K^{-yr}), *Clarias lazera* has the highest value at 1.8, indicating a faster growth rate. The mean length values revealed that the species has 15 cm, The growth performance index (ϕ') was 2.10 which is optimum, In terms of hypothetical lifespan (T_{max}), the species had a T_{max} value of 1.2 years. Table 2.

TABLE 2. The growth parameters of *Clarias lazera* collected from sampling site (malleri water body)

Fish species	L_{∞}	K^{-yr}	$L-L^1$	ϕ'	T_{max}
<i>C. Lazera</i>	39.90	1.8	15	2.10	1.8

Where: L_{∞} = Describe the **maximum length** a fish can attain if it were to grow forever (in centimeters)

K^{-yr} = the growth speed or growth constant of a fish species per year

$L-L^1$ = Mean length (the minimum length the fish species is supposed to be caught)

ϕ' = the growth performance index of a fish species and

T_{max} The hypothetical lifespan of a fish species

Figure 2. Monthly variation in Fish length of Catfish (*Clarias lazera*) in river gongola (malleri area)

Monthly recruitment

The recruitment rates of the fish species were estimated by projecting backward along a trajectory defined by the Von Bertalanffy Growth Formula (VBGF), using the FiSAT software routine. This involved aligning length frequencies to the time axis of a series of samples using the original data, following the method outlined in the FiSAT routine. Growth parameters such as L_{∞} and K were inputted to facilitate recruitment determination. The resulting output provided recruitment pulses, which are the months with the highest recruitment percentages (Asriyana *et al.*; 2020).

The monthly recruitment strength and the ideal length at first maturity (L_m) for the fish species are presented in Figure 3. According to the table, two significant peaks are observed in the recruitment strength one in March/April and the other in July/August." indicating bi-modal recruitment (two main recruitment seasons within the year)

The ideal length at first maturity (L_m) for the species as indicated by the recorded values reflects the size at which the fish species typically reach early maturity. These findings highlight the reproductive timing and maturity characteristics of the species.

Figure 3. Monthly recruitment strength for *Clarias lazera*

The fish species mortality parameters

Using Pauly's Mortality Equation, the total mortality rate (Z) for each fish species was calculated through Length-Converted Catch Analysis, with an assumed mean annual surface temperature of the reservoir at 25°C. The natural mortality rate (M) was also derived using Pauly's equation. Alongside Z and M , this process also produced values for fishing mortality (F) and exploitation rate (E). The exploitation rate (E) was determined using F/Z . Probabilities of capture (L_{25} , L_{50} , and L_{75}) were derived from the Length-Converted Catch Curve using a running average, representing the lengths at which 25%, 50%, and 75% of the population are susceptible to fishing gear. Here, L_{50} was also considered the length at first maturity for recruitment purposes (Olopade *et al.*; 2019)

The table reveals that total mortality (Z) for *Clarias lazera* was found to be 3.38 while mortality-to-growth ratio (Z/K) showed a maximum value of 1.493.

The interpretation of Z/K values is as follows:

$Z/K > 1$ indicates that mortality exceeds growth.

$Z/K = 1$ signifies a balance between growth and mortality.

$Z/K < 1$ implies growth dominance.

$Z/K = 2$ reflects exponentially high mortality rates.

From the analysis, it is observed that 0.22% of the fish population represents growth dominance, 0.00235% indicates mortality dominance, and 99.868% reflects exponential mortality relative to growth. These findings underscore the high impact of mortality on the fish species, with *Clarias lazera* showing a more significant mortality-to-growth relationship compared to other species (Table 4).

Mortality parameters, which describe the depletion of fish populations due to fishing or natural causes, include total mortality (Z^{yr}), mortality relative to growth (Z/K), natural mortality (M^{yr}), fishing mortality (F^{yr}), exploitation rate (E), and probabilities of capture such as (L_{25}), (L_{50}), and (L_{75}). These parameters are summarized in Table 4.

In terms of natural mortality (Z^{yr}), *Clarias lazera* exhibited greater susceptibility to natural causes of death, with a natural mortality index of 2.29. Regarding depletion through fishing activities (F^{yr}), the data

presented in Table 4. Indicates that *Clarias lazera* had a low fishing mortality index $F^{yr} = 1.09$, reflecting lower fishing pressure on the species.

The current exploitation rate (E) reveals that *Clarias lazera* had a lower exploitation rate ($E = 0.24$).

The probabilities of capture, represented by (L_{25}), (L_{50}), and (L_{75}), describe the lengths at which 25%, 50%, and 75% of the fish population become vulnerable to fishing gear. For (L_{25}), *Clarias lazera* displayed the length at vulnerability of (11.24 cm), However, a similar pattern was observed for (L_{50}), where *Clarias lazera* recorded an (L_{50}) of 13.79 cm. This result highlight fishing vulnerability based on species and size thresholds (Table 4.).

TABLE 3. The mortality parameters of Catfish (*Clarias lazera*)a

Fish species	Z^{yr}	Z/K^{yr}	M^{yr}	F^{yr}	E	Probability of capture		
						L_{20}	L_{50}	L_{75}
<i>Clarias lazera</i>	2.90	1.493	2.21	1.09	0.24	11.24	13.79	15.65

Where:

Z = Total mortality, M = Natural mortality, F = Fishing mortality E = Exploitation rate, L_{25} = length at which 25% of the population will be vulnerable to fishing gear, L_{50} (Rrecruitment length) = length at which 50% of the population will be vulnerable to fishing gear, L_{75} = length at which 75% of the population will be vulnerable to fishing gear, Z/K = Status Extent of mortality

DISCUSSION

Length-weight relationships

The length-weight relationships of fish species in the Malleri water body revealed isometric growth based on the corresponding b - exponents. The analyzed fish species generally conformed to the expected allometric coefficient b - values (3.0). However, a negative allometric growth pattern was observed in Size Structures, Length-Weight Relationships and Condition Factors of *Synodontis obesus* (Boulenger, 1898: Siluiformes, Mochokidae) with b -values of 2.497 and 2.617 during the dry season consistent with findings from the Lower Cross River, Nigeria (Etitigwun *et al.*, 2023).

This deviation from isometric growth may be attributed to factors such as sample size and the use of small-mesh-size fishing gear, which could influence the size distribution and growth patterns of the sampled fish.

The present study referenced two studies that demonstrated positive allometry based on their corresponding b – *index* values. In this research, a positive allometry was also observed, with the highest b -index aligning with findings from studies on *S. berak* (3.14) and *S. namak* (3.09) in Iranian inland waters (Poorbagher *et al.*, 2023). The observed allometric deviations may be attributed to favorable environmental conditions, the predominance of medium-sized individuals with high growth potential, efficient food conversion, and biomass accumulation. These factors likely contributed to the positive growth attributes observed in the species population.

In general, fish growth patterns are closely tied to the exponential values (b) of length-weight relationships (LWR), which are subject to change based on various factors. These changes are influenced by environmental parameters such as seasonal temperature fluctuations, habitat availability, optimal temperature conditions, sufficient food supply, and seasonal variations. High concentrations of dissolved oxygen and effective water circulation also play a crucial role in supporting fish growth (Damora *et al.*, 2020). These factors are particularly relevant to the fish species analyzed in this study. The b -value serves as an indicator of the productivity of the originating water body, as highlighted by Damora *et al.* (2020).

This underscores the importance of maintaining favorable environmental conditions to support healthy fish populations and sustain ecosystem productivity.

Growth Parameters of Catfish (*Clarias lazera*) in the malleri water body

The widely used and reliable dataset that provides valuable insights into the life history of fish, making it a preferred method for estimating growth parameters is length-frequency data (Amponsah *et al.*, 2021). This approach provides a robust framework for understanding the population dynamics and growth trends of the target species, contributing to more informed fishery management strategies.

Clarias lazera

The analysis of this study indicates that *Clarias lazera* has an asymptotic length $L_{\infty} = 39.90\text{cm}$ a growth coefficient $K = 1.8\text{yr}^{-1}$, potential longevity of 1.8 years, and a growth performance index (\dot{O}) = 1.00. These indices align partially with the findings of Abdalla *et al.* (2024), who reported $L_{\infty} = 42\text{cm}$ (\dot{O}) = 2.937 $K = 0.490\text{yr}^{-1}$, and a potential longevity $T_{\text{max}} = 5.604$ years for *Labeo senegalensis* from the Khashm El-Girba Reservoir, Sudan. Similarly, Amponsah *et al.* (2021) recorded $L_{\infty} = 39.6\text{cm}$ (\dot{O}) = 2.484 \), and $K = 0.19\text{yr}^{-1}$ for the Lesser African Threadfin from Ghana's coastal waters, indicating both larger and smaller growth indices compared to the present study.

Disparities in Growth Parameters

The variations in growth parameters across these studies can be attributed to several factors, including differences in habitat characteristics (Moniruzzaman *et al.*, 2021), availability of diverse food resources, efficient digestion mechanisms, and species-specific resilience to diseases. Additionally, exponential growth rates supported by a wide range of dietary inputs could contribute to higher growth indices in some environments.

5.2.4 Morphological and gear-related considerations

The morphology of *Clarias lazera* makes them less susceptible to capture at juvenile stages using legal fishing gears, unless non-selective or illicit gear is employed. This characteristic might explain some of the observed growth trends, as larger individuals tend to dominate harvests. These findings underscore the need to enforce regulations on gear usage to prevent unsustainable exploitation of juvenile stocks, ensuring population stability and ecological balance.

Mortality indices of Catfish (*Clarias lazera*) in the malleri water body

This section will focus on key mortality indices, including natural mortality (M), fishing mortality (F), total mortality (Z), exploitation ratio (E), length at first capture (Lc or L_{50}), recruitment pattern, and asymptotic length (L_{∞}) for fish species in the Malleri water body. Other mortality indices may also be discussed where applicable; these indices play a critical role in understanding the dynamics of fish populations and their responses to both natural and fishing-related pressures. They provide insights into the sustainability of fisheries, the impact of fishing on fish stocks, and the overall health of the aquatic ecosystem, by examining these parameters, we can assess the level of exploitation of fish species, the effectiveness of fisheries management strategies, and the need for conservation measures to ensure that fish populations remain viable over time.

***Clarias lazera*:**

The length at first recruitment/maturity (LM) in *Clarias lazera* aligns with the length at first capture (Lc), which suggests that most of the fish being landed have reached the first stage of maturity. This is further supported by a reproductive load (L_v/L_{∞}) of 0.74, indicating that a significant proportion of the population at landing is reproductively mature. However, the exploitation rate (E), along with the E_{max} values (B/R and Y/R), surpass the threshold of 0.5, which points to overexploitation of the species. The L_{opt} value of 36.4 cm indicates the optimal size for fishing; exceeding this threshold could result in the fragmentation of the population.

The mortality dominance index ($Z/K = 1.493 > 1$) further emphasizes that the dominant factor in the population's mortality is fishing activities, with fishing mortality (F) at 0.69% per year. This suggests that fishing practices are placing significant pressure on the species, leading to potential sustainability concerns.

When compared to the study by Doinsing *et al.*, (2021) on *Tegillarca granosa* from Marudu Bay, Malaysia, the mortality indices show some contrasts, with $Z = 2.39$, $M = 1.32$, $F = 1.07$, and an $E = 0.45$, which reflects heavy overexploitation in both cases, highlighting the species' high demand. Despite the differences in specific values, both studies indicate significant overfishing pressures.

Considering these findings, reducing the fishing pressure by 20 to 25% could increase the Maximum Sustainable Yield (MSY) by about 30%, which would benefit the long-term sustainability of the stock. The current reproductive load ($L_v/L_\infty = 0.74$) is promising, suggesting that the population has a good capacity to replenish rapidly. Additionally, bimodal reproductive peaks in February–March and October reflect the species' typical reproductive patterns, which is common among African fish species. This could provide a window of opportunity for adjusting fishing strategies to ensure that the species' reproductive cycles are not disrupted.

Virtual population analysis (VPA) of Catfish (*Clarias lazera*) in the malleri water body

The Virtual Population Analysis (VPA) in this study revealed significant insights into the fishing dynamics of *Clarias lazera*. The species also showed the least fishing mortality ($F = 1.09$) at its least length-class (LLC) of 16.29 cm, indicating relatively lower fishing pressure. These findings point to recruitment overfishing, where the fishing mortality (F) exceeds the sustainable rate, depleting the population before it can fully recruit or reach its optimal size. *Clarias lazera* however experiences lower fishing mortality, but still reflect concerns around fishing practices that may impede the long-term health of the population.

The outcomes of this study align with the findings of Amponsah *et al.* (2019), which similarly pointed to heavy exploitation of *Oreochromis niloticus* due to the use of non-selective gears and unregulated fishing. The high volume of fish within the 16.29 cm length-class for *Oreochromis niloticus* further confirms that juvenile fish are being heavily exploited, a trend associated with poor fisheries management practices. Overall, the study confirms the need for better fishing regulations, including gear restrictions and mesh-size controls, to prevent further overfishing and ensure that both species can maintain healthy, sustainable populations in the Malleri water body.

5.5 CONCLUSION

This study investigated the population dynamics of key fish species *Catfish (Clarias lazera)*, in the Malleri section of the River Gongola in Gombe State, Nigeria. The primary objective was to assess crucial population parameters, including length-weight frequencies, growth patterns, recruitment patterns, and mortality indices. These findings aim to provide valuable insights into the status of the fish populations, their ecological roles, and potential sustainability challenges. The results are intended to inform the development of effective fisheries management practices in the region, contributing to the conservation and sustainable use of aquatic resources.

The research revealed that *Clarias lazera* (Catfish) exhibit distinct length-weight relationships and growth rates, essential indicators of population health and productivity. The analysis of length-weight frequencies showed significant variation in fish sizes within the population. Notably, certain age groups were overrepresented, suggesting the influence of selective fishing pressures or seasonal recruitment variations. Using a dataset of 659 specimens, growth parameters were calculated via the Powell-Wetherall plot option in FiSAT II software to determine the initial asymptotic length (L_∞). This was subsequently applied to the Von Bertalanffy Growth Function (VBGF) to derive the growth coefficient (K). Results indicated that *Clarias lazera* has an L_∞ of (39.90 cm) and a growth coefficient (K) of 1.80 yr^{-1} .

The findings suggested a 52% ratio of good growth speed through the species. Catfish displayed a relatively steady growth pattern.

The recruitment patterns, analyzed using the “recruitment” option in FiSAT, showed that the species had two recruitment peaks per year. This is beneficial for replenishing stocks affected by mortalities. However, many individuals were harvested before reaching table size, raising concerns about unsustainable fishing practices that could impact long-term population viability.

The analysis of mortality indices revealed that fishing mortality rates (F^{yr}) were notably high for the species *Clarias lazera* (Catfish), underscoring the impact of unsustainable fishing practices. Such practices risk depleting fish populations faster than they can naturally replenish, emphasizing the urgent need for regulatory measures to ensure sustainable exploitation and to safeguard juvenile fish from overharvesting.

Using the “Length Converted Catch Curve” option in FiSAT II software, the mortality parameters for the species was assessed. Key findings included: Natural Mortality (M^{yr}): *Clarias lazera*: 2.21 yr^{-1} . Fishing Mortality (F^{yr}) *Clarias lazera* 1.09 yr^{-1} , indicating exploitation within safe limits.

These results highlight the need for targeted management practices, such as implementing seasonal fishing bans, using selective gear, and enforcing minimum size limits. Such measures can improve fishing pressure on Catfish, which is particularly vulnerable to overexploitation, while maintaining sustainable harvest levels.

5.6 RECOMMENDATIONS

To address the challenges identified in this study and ensure sustainable fishery management in the Malleri water body, the following recommendations were proposed:

1. Size and Sex-based Variations in LWR

Investigating the LWR differences between male and female fish, as well as across different size classes, will provide insights into potential variations in growth allocation between sexes and developmental stages.

2. Age and Growth Studies Using Otolith and Scale Analysis

Further research should incorporate otolith and scale readings to determine the age structure of fish populations, allowing for a more precise analysis of growth trends and life expectancy

3. Spawning and Breeding Cycles in Relation to Recruitment

Understanding the breeding periodicity and spawning success of *C. lazera* through gonad maturation studies will help correlate spawning periods with recruitment peaks

4. Length-at-First Capture (L_c) and Gear Selectivity Impact

Determine L_c using probability of capture analysis to assess whether fishing gear is selectively removing immature fish, which could lead to recruitment overfishing and Study the effectiveness of different fishing gears and their impact on mortality rates.

5. Strict Enforcement of Fisheries Laws:

Ensure unbiased and effective enforcement of fishing regulations, such as prohibiting the use of non-selective fishing gears. Regular monitoring and penalties for violations should be implemented to promote compliance.

By implementing these recommendations, the sustainability of the Malleri water body and its fishery resources can be enhanced, benefiting both the ecosystem and the local community.

5.6 Contributions to Knowledge

1. This study presents species-specific length-weight frequency data for *Clarias lazera* in Malleri water body, which had not been previously documented, thereby providing a baseline for future fisheries and ecological studies in the region.
2. It establishes size distribution patterns and growth trends of the two species, which can be used by fisheries managers to evaluate stock status and implement size-based harvesting regulations in similar inland water systems.
3. The research provides species-specific growth parameters such as growth coefficient (K), asymptotic length (L_∞), and growth performance index (Φ') for *Clarias lazera* in Malleri water body information that was previously unavailable for this location.
4. It contributes to the understanding of species growth dynamics in a savanna inland water body, serving as a scientific basis for stock assessment models and sustainable fishery management practices in the region.

5. The study documents the recruitment patterns of *C. lazera* identifying the periods of peak recruitment and thus aiding in the determination of optimal fishing seasons or potential closed seasons.
6. It enhances understanding of population replenishment dynamics in the Malleri water body, which is essential for formulating long-term management strategies to ensure species sustainability. This research is among the first to quantify natural, fishing, and total mortality (M, F, Z) of *Clarias lazera* in Malleri water body, filling a knowledge gap in inland fisheries stock assessment in Gombe State.
7. By estimating the exploitation rate (E), the study informs whether current fishing practices are sustainable or if regulatory measures are needed to prevent overfishing

REFERENCES

- Wake, A. A., and Geleto, T. C. (2019). Socio-economic importance of Fish production and consumption status in Ethiopia: A review. *International Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Studies*, 7(4), 206-211.
- Gebremedhin, S., Bruneel, S., Getahun, A., Anteneh, W., and Goethals, P. (2021). Scientific methods to understand fish population dynamics and support sustainable fisheries management. *Water*, 13(4), 574. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13040574>
- Nazeef, S., and Yerima, R. (2023). Interpretation of Allometric Growth Patterns of Fish Species From Dadin-Kowa Reservoir. *Bima Journal of Science And Technology (2536-6041)*, 7(01), 62-71. <https://doi.org/10.56892/bima.v7i01.389>
- Ahti, P. A., Kuparinen, A., and Uusi-Heikkilä, S. (2020). Size does Matter—the eco-evolutionary effects of changing body size in fish. *Environmental Reviews*, 28(3), 311-324.
- Abd El-Hack, M. E., El-Saadony, M. T., Nader, M. M., Salem, H. M., El-Tahan, A. M., Soliman, S. M., and Khafaga, A. F. (2022). Effect of environmental factors on growth performance of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *International Journal of Biometeorology*, 66(11), 2183-2194.
- Gatto, J. V., and Trexler, J. C. (2019). Seasonality of fish recruitment in a pulsed floodplain ecosystem: Estimation and hydrological controls. *Environmental Biology of Fishes*, 102, 595-613. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10641-019-00856-9>
- Zymarioieva, A., Bondarev, D., Kunakh, O., Svenning, J. C., and Zhukov, O. (2024). Young-of-the-year fish as bioindicators of eutrophication and temperature regime of water bodies. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 196(2), 161.
- Liu, S., Xie, M., Wang, P., Deng, Q., Zhang, Z., Wu, H., ... and Xie, Z. (2024). Allometric Growth Pattern and Hunger Tolerance of *Hemibarbus maculatus* Bleeker Larvae. *Biology*, 13(3), 164. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology13030164>
- Rodríguez-García, C., Castro-Gutiérrez, J., Domínguez-Bustos, Á. R., García-González, A., & Cabrera-Castro, R. (2023). Every fish counts: Challenging length–weight relationship bias in discards. *Fishes*, 8(5), 222.
- Lai, H. L., Gallucci, V. F., Gunderson, D. R., and Donnelly, R. F. (2023). Age determination in fisheries: methods and applications to stock assessment. In *Stock Assessment* (pp. 82-178). CRC Press. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.1201/9781003421252-3/age-determination-fisheries-methods-applications-stock-assessment-han-lin-lai-vincent-gallucci-donald-gunderson-robert-donnelly>
- Camp, E., Collins, A. B., Ahrens, R. N., and Lorenzen, K. (2020). Fish population recruitment: what recruitment means and why it matters: FA222, 3/2020. *EDIS*, 2020(2), 6-6. [file:///C:/Users/hp/Downloads/dihagan,+FA22200%20\(2\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/hp/Downloads/dihagan,+FA22200%20(2).pdf)
- Hou, G., Wang, J., Chen, Z., Zhou, J., Huang, W., and Zhang, H. (2020). Molecular and morphological identification and seasonal distribution of eggs of four Decapterus fish species in the northern South China Sea: a key to conservation of spawning ground. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 7, 590564. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/marine-science/articles/10.3389/fmars.2020.590564/full>
- Geromont, H., and Butterworth, D. (2022). A review of assessment methods and the development of management procedures for data-poor fisheries.
- Arevalo, E., Cabral, H. N., Villeneuve, B., Possémé, C., and Lepage, M. (2023). Fish larvae dynamics in temperate estuaries: A review on processes, patterns and factors that determine recruitment. *Fish and Fisheries*, 24(3), 466-487. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/faf.12740>

- Ferreira, A. O., Azevedo, O. M., Barroso, C., Duarte, S., Egas, C., Fontes, J. T., ... & Costa, F. O. (2024). Multi-marker DNA metabarcoding for precise species identification in ichthyoplankton samples. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 19772.
- Björnsson, B., Sólmundsson, J., and Woods, P. J. (2022). Natural mortality in exploited fish stocks: annual variation estimated with data from trawl surveys. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 79(5), 1569-1582. <https://academic.oup.com/icesjms/article/79/5/1569/6590896>
- Calì, F. (2024). Adaptive life history strategies of the Adriatic commercial Gadiformes facing fishing pressure and climate change. Adaptive life history strategies of the Adriatic commercial Gadiformes facing fishing pressure and climate change (unibo.it)
- Babangida, S., Rukaiya, H., Abubakar, B., & Muhammad, I. (2024). Prevalence Of Snail Vectors Of Schistosomiasis Along Antau River, Keffi, Nasarawa State. *International Journal Of Nature And Science Advance Research*
- (Remote sensing and GIS Laboratory Department of Geography, Gombe State University 2024)
- Mendoza, G. C., & Vigilia, E. G. R. (2024). An Assessment of Some Meristic and Metric Characteristics and Biological Indices of the Introduced Largemouth Bass (*Micropterus salmoides*) in Pantabangan Reservoir, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. *Uttar pradesh journal of zoology*, 45(16), 173-188
- Vicentin, W., Tondato, K. K., Silva Ferreira, F., Costa, F. E. D. S., and Suárez, Y. R. (2018). Population parameters and reproduction of the piranha *Serrasalmus marginatus* in the Negro river, Pantanal, Brazil. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 34(5), 1136-1144. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/jai.13770>
- Asriyana, A., Halili, H., & Irawati, N. (2020). Size structure and growth parameters of striped eel catfish (*Plotosus lineatus*) in Kolono Bay, Southeast Sulawesi, Indonesia. *Aquaculture, Aquarium, Conservation & Legislation*, 13(1), 268-279.
- Olopade, O., Dienye, H., and Bamidele, N. A. (2019). Some Population Parameters of the *Sardinella maderensis* (Lowe, 1838) in the Sombreiro River of Niger Delta. *Acta Aquatica Turcica*, 15(3), 354-364. <https://doi.org/10.22392/actaquatr.532284>
- Etitigwun, J., Micheal, O., and Glory, N. (2023). Size Structures, Length-Weight Relationships and Condition Factors of *Synodontis obesus* (Boulenger, 1898: Siluriformes, Mochokidae) in the Lower Cross River, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Biology*, 17(2), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajob/2023/v17i2317>
- Damora, A., Batubara, A. S., Zuhdi, Z., Restiangsih, Y., Amir, F., Irham, M., ... and Rizal, R. (2020). Diversity of marine fish and their conservation status in Pusong Bay, Lhokseumawe City, Aceh Province, Indonesia. *European Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 10(2), 115-123. <https://doi.org/10.14712/23361964.2020.13>
- Amponsah S, Ofori-danson P, Nunoo F, Ameyaw G. (2019) Estimates of Population parameters for *Sardinella maderensis* (Lowe, 1838) in the coastal waters of Ghana. *Greener J Agric Sci*. 2019;9(1):23-31.
- Moniruzzaman, M., Bhowmick, A. R., Karan, S., and Mukherjee, J. (2021). Spatial heterogeneity within habitat indicates the community assemblage pattern and life strategies. *Ecological indicators*, 123, 107365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.107365>
- Doinsing, J. W., Admodisastro, V. A., Duisan, L., and Ransangan, J. (2021). Population dynamics and condition index of natural stock of blood cockle, *Tegillarca granosa* (Mollusca, Bivalvia, Arcidae) in the Marudu Bay, Malaysia. *Acta Oceanologica Sinica*, 40(8), 89-97. Population dynamics and condition index of natural stock of blood cockle, *Tegillarca granosa* (Mollusca, Bivalvia, Arcidae) in the Marudu Bay, Malaysia | *Acta Oceanologica Sinica* (springer.com)